

MODERN DIGITAL SKILLS AND COMPETENCE**Tekesbayeva N.A.***Kazakh National Women's Teacher Training University***Abstract**

The implementation of digital tools is widely used in all spheres of life, including the educational environment. This article examines the structure and characteristics of existing digital educational tools, the current state of digitization in educational environments.

Keywords: MOOC, LMS, LCMS, digital education, digital competence, methodology, gamification

Introduction

With the development of information technology, the use of digital tools in various areas of life is becoming a common practice. Digitization has also affected the educational process. New technologies, including mobile technologies, are used more in education than ever before. Learners are also increasingly using digital tools to solve their problems. Currently, there are many information systems that are directly or indirectly used in the educational process. Often, such systems are used to facilitate the learning process, to visualize the explained material, to facilitate testing processes or exams. Examples of such systems include platforms for remote deployment: for example, MOOC (Massive open online course), learning process organization systems, learning process management in the form of commercial products or digital modular systems developed in certain educational institutions. Given the existence and expansion of such systems, it will be necessary to structure and describe them in order to further design and develop such systems. In addition, the role of the teacher in such systems, as well as the working mechanisms of the two parties in the educational structure - the teacher and the student - remain unclear. That is, the purpose of writing this article was to determine the change of the teacher's role in the learning process under the condition of using digital educational tools.

Materials and methods

The methodology of this work consisted of the analysis of literary sources on the given issue. Taking into account the set goal and the established methodology, the objectives of this study were as follows:

- analysis of literature and study of the current level of digitization of society, identification of parties involved in the educational process;
- analysis of the experience of introduction and use of digital tools in education;
- study of digital innovative tools used in the field of education;
- conclusion based on research results.

The large-scale and rapid emergence, development and implementation of new technologies and information systems have inevitably led to changes in the world economy, and important social changes are taking place. Many researchers have begun to think seriously about the impact of digitization on public life. Thus, most researchers agree that new digital technologies will replace manual labor, the working population

will improve or change their skills, and will be employed in enterprises and industries in other areas of activity that are more related to social interaction.

Many learners find modern education to be a monotonous and even boring process, and game elements can help create artificial motivation for learning. In addition, scientists note that despite the widespread introduction of game experiences in various spheres of life (marketing, business, etc.), gamification of education has not yet taken place [1].

Gamification elements can be used by computer science teachers, and the fact that teachers of other disciplines do not have the necessary technologies to create and implement game elements leads to a big problem. Thus, the introduction of game elements into education is still an understudied process, which requires certain suitable technological conditions and the development of appropriate software products.

In order for learners to have effective interactive learning, it is necessary to provide access to the widest possible range of different interactive environments or programs. That is, in addition to equipping the classroom or acquiring various software and technologies of educational institutions within the framework of traditional education, it is necessary to develop software products for mobile learning opportunities. The emergence of new technologies for teachers is associated with the need for constant professional development. This forces them to adapt to new paradigms of education and to reconstruct their methodology and approaches. Taking into account the active implementation of digital learning environments and e-learning, as mentioned above, the problem of changing the role of the teacher in the educational process arises.

Today, new programs for the development of "smart cities" are being actively implemented in the world, including the tasks of digitalization of the economy, laws and projects on the use of digital data and technologies. However, there is a limited number of publications that examine the direct impact of such programs on learners and teachers in the teaching of various professions.

Many researchers believe that new digital technologies will significantly change the professional practice of teachers and the area of responsibility in the learning process, but the process of teacher education should not change significantly to adapt to such changes. The teacher is the main person in the educational structure within the framework of the traditional teaching con-

cept. Improving the competence of teachers to use digital tools in their work is necessary for the learning process and will be beneficial for the teachers themselves. In order for teachers to communicate with students in the "same language" in the future, it is necessary to constantly improve their level of digital competence and adopt the concept of continuous education in the context of current changes [2].

Digital competence is the knowledge and skills needed to use technology in the process of creating and formalizing new knowledge. In addition, teachers face significant challenges in the process of teaching digital tools. This suggests that teachers need to better integrate technology as a pedagogical tool to encourage the use of digital technologies within their professional didactic competence, and that such educational units should be included in teacher professional development programs. At the same time, there is a problem with integrating the training of "digital competences" into teacher education institutions, as the content of the program may be outdated by the time it is finally approved and implemented. Therefore, attention should be paid to digital competence, which includes not only the mastery of tools, but also the teacher's awareness of how to use technology critically and reflexively in the process of generating new knowledge.

To meet the demands of today's economy and labor market, education must go beyond traditional approaches. Let's look at examples of automated digital technologies used in the learning process in different countries and what opportunities they provide for teachers and learners.

1. Modular digital educational environments. Some educational institutions and companies create their own digitally integrated modular learning environments. One of them is PIES (Personalized Integrated Education System). The system is currently under development. It provides full functionality to learners, teachers, parents and other stakeholders. Given the use of such a system, the role of the teacher in the learner-centered paradigm shifts to that of a mediator or mentor. The teacher selects and designs learning materials for students in the above-mentioned modular systems [3].

2. One of the most modern educational projects is MOOC (massive online open course). MOOC platforms can also be called tools and digital environments. Recently, the participation of universities in creating online courses is high both in Kazakhstan and in the world. Currently, more than 48 million learners are enrolled in the world's most popular online MOOC platforms (Coursera, edX, FutureLearn and Udacity). In addition, the practice of creating and developing

MOOCs is only at the initial stage, so currently online courses are free, only a certificate of completion is paid.

One of the main problems with MOOCs is the low completion rate – only about 10% of learners complete the online course. Furthermore, there is currently little empirical research on the actual effectiveness of MOOCs. It is unclear for which subjects online courses are an effective form of education and for which their model is not suitable. A limiting factor in the development of the widespread distribution of MOOCs is the lack of a teacher to guide the learning process and, as a result, the necessary feedback for an effective educational process. In online courses, the absence of a motivating factor in the person of a teacher or mentor leads to the failure of participants to complete the course. In addition, currently, not all platforms attract relevant qualified specialists when creating courses, for example, the stepic.org platform, which is mainly located on the border between a MOOC and a simple educational platform. Stepic provides access to courses that anyone can do, regardless of skill level.

Despite considerable formal differences between structural organization and platform interfaces, the format of all known MOOC platforms includes the use of video lectures and test questions with multiple choice, open and closed questions. There are no opportunities and functionality to integrate additional tools, for example, adding gamification elements to the educational process, which can increase user participation [4].

3. LMS (learning management system) systems implemented by programs such as LCMS (learning content management system) are also used to organize the distance learning process. These are learning management systems used to develop, manage, and distribute online learning materials in a shared user experience. LMS creates a unified learning space for theoretical knowledge, active practice and personal teacher feedback. Such systems also allow instructors to create courses in a visual virtual environment. The teacher can determine the learning trajectory of the student, as well as the order of reading the material. Some of the most successful examples of LMS systems are systems such as Adobe Captivate Prime, Moodle, Claroline, and others. Here the role of the teacher is not equalized, the contribution remains the same as the participation of the teacher in the educational process with the concept of traditional teaching, but the educational process itself is transferred to the digital environment.

Let's put together a summary table with all the characteristics of digital learning environments. Figure 1 shows a schematic diagram of teacher-student interaction through an educational environment.

Pic. 1 Schematic diagram of teacher and student interaction

In all types of educational system, the student receives information from the teacher about the course and monitoring work. Only in LMS and LCMS and modular systems it receives course recommendations from the instructor. In turn, the teacher can access information about the student's activity in LMS and LCMS and modular systems, and receive reports on his progress. In the case of MOOC courses, the teacher creates the course and the test blocks for it only once, with no further interaction or monitoring of the learner's actions [4].

Taking into account the unwavering role of the teacher as a mentor or assistant in the learning process, it is necessary to develop a teacher training system to promote the introduction of digital technologies into the educational process, even in non-traditional teaching models. In addition, training courses, trainings and seminars on improving the "digital literacy" of teachers are in demand in the future and require careful and detailed research as new teaching technologies emerge. The development of such criteria can solve the problem of determining the need or lack of mastery of this particular competence.

Structuring information about educational systems can also help to solve the problems of training and professional development of staff, as it helps to create their own training system for future teachers or to improve the skills of experienced staff.

Result

As a result of the study, it was determined that digital education standards will include the use of automated and digital educational tools in the future. In addition to the standard, there is also the influence of society, because now most of the students cannot imagine their life without gadgets and digital tools. Nowadays, digital learning environments cannot function successfully without the involvement of the teacher. However,

there is no clear definition of the term "digital competence" that does not allow to assess the level of mastery of new technologies of teachers.

Thus, due to the presence of the necessary technologies for the successful implementation of the concept of education in the future, it is necessary to establish a permanent transfer of new educational technologies to the educational process, to introduce digital environments and tools into the educational system. The general educational process, the development of digital competence criteria and the creation of a continuous professional development program for teachers so that the educational process can keep pace with the development of technology.

References

1. Nadiia Voronova. 2019. Digital educational resources in the theory and practice of modern foreign education. *Professionalism of the Teacher: Theoretical and Methodological Aspects*9 (Jul. 2019), 37–47.
2. Maryna Ivashchenko and Oleksii Samoylenko. 2021. Digital educational environment: using the power of self-competence education to improve the effectiveness of bachelor's degree in management and administration. *Conference on professional development of specialists in the digitized society: current trends (PDSDig-2020). Scientific and practical conference with international participation: proceedings (selected papers) November 12th-13th, 2020, Zhytomyr*, 110–121.
3. Valeeva N. G., Rudneva M. A. Massovye otrkrytye onlayn-kursy v obuchenii studentov ekologicheskogo fakul'teta angliyskomu yazyku dlya professional'noy kommunikatsii. *Vestnik Rossiyskogo universiteta druzhby narodov. Seriya: Ekologiya i bezopasnost' zhiznedeyatel'nosti*. 2016. No. 3.
4. Uribe P. N., Vaughan M. Facilitating student learning in distance education: a case study on the development and implementation of a multifaceted feedback system. *Distance Education*.2017.Vol.38.No.3.P.288–301